

A Ground Fault Location Method for DC Systems Through Multiple Grounding Connections

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Abstract—Direct current (dc) systems have an increasingly important role in electrical systems, especially photovoltaic (PV) solar power plants and battery storage systems as they are essential for the development of more sustainable, efficient, and reliable electrical systems. PV panels and batteries are generally composed of multiple series-parallel cells. This fact makes their fault diagnosis challenging, especially against ground faults as these systems are generally ungrounded. In this article, a ground fault location method for dc sources with multiple series-parallel cells is proposed. It estimates the faulty branch, the faulty cell location inside this branch and its fault resistance. The method is based on the output current measurement of each branch and on the voltage measurement on a grounding resistor, which is switched between three positions: the positive, the midpoint and the negative terminals of the protected dc system. To validate it, several computer simulations and experimental tests on a battery pack have been carried out. The results obtained proves an excellent performance for faulty cell location and fault resistance estimation, although further investigations are required to better discern the faulty branch.

Index Terms—Batteries, dc–ac power converters, fault diagnosis, fault location, photovoltaic (PV) systems, power system security.

NOMENCLATURE

C	Converter’s capacitor.
C_1	Polarization capacitance 1.
C_2	Polarization capacitance 2.
C_{Snubber}	Snubber capacitance of the converter.
I_{DCF}	DC faulty branch current.
I_{DCH}	DC healthy branch current.
k	Ground fault location [pu].

0:	Negative terminal/1: positive terminal.
L	Inductive load
L_{filter}	Inductive filter.
L_w	Wire inductance.
R	Resistive load.
R_0	Ohmic resistance.
R_1	Polarization resistance 1.
R_2	Polarization resistance 2.
R_f	Fault resistance.
R_{gnd}	Grounding resistor.
R_{int}	Converter’s internal resistance.
R_{Snubber}	Snubber resistance of the converter.
R_w	Wire resistance.
t_d	Dead time.
U_{Cell}	Cell voltage.
U_{DC}	DC total voltage.
U_{gnd}	Grounding resistor voltage.
$U_{\text{gnd}+}$	Grounding resistor voltage in positive terminal connection.
$U_{\text{gnd}M}$	Grounding resistor voltage in midpoint terminal connection.
$U_{\text{gnd}-}$	Grounding resistor voltage in negative terminal connection.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS, the use of direct current (dc) in power systems is steadily increasing due to the integration of renewable energy sources [1]. In this field, two main dc systems highlights: on the one hand, photovoltaic (PV) power plants, that have been massively adopted as the most common type of distributed generation [2], and on the other hand, electric storage systems, such as electrochemical batteries, to ensure the system reliability against the uncertainty of renewable energy production [3].

These dc systems are normally composed of low voltage cells, batteries, or capacitors, connected in series-parallel, normally without any grounded point [4], [5], [6]. These series-parallel connections make very difficult the diagnosis of possible electric faults [6], [7]. The more the number of series-parallel cells are, the more challenging is the system diagnosis.

The ground faults are the most common types of faults in power systems [8]. They are typically caused by the insulation aging process, overheats or overcurrent events [7]. In an ungrounded system (e.g., a battery pack, a variable speed drive or a PV power plant), a single ground fault could not provoke any damage since there is not any current return path [9]. However,

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if the first fault is not eliminated and a new ground fault occurs, a short circuit current would appear causing devastating damages [6]. In order to detect the first ground fault before a second one happens, some methods have been developed for dc systems, such as for HVdc [10], dc microgrids [11], dc power traction systems [12], PV panels [13], or batteries [14].

In this article, a ground faults location method for dc systems with multiple series-parallel cells is presented. The method is based on a grounding resistor which is sequentially connected between the positive, the negative and the midpoint terminals of the dc systems and ground by three different switches. The presented method can estimate the ground fault location, its fault resistance, and the faulty parallel branch. Besides, this method proves to have a good fault sensibility regardless of the fault position. This is an important advantage in comparison to single point grounding approaches, which reduce their sensibility as the ground fault occurs closer to the grounding point. The method was briefly presented in its conference form in [15], and also, it was granted with a Spanish patent [16].

This article is organized as follows: Section II provides a brief state of the art of previous ground fault detection techniques. Section III explains the fundamentals of the proposed method. Section IV and Section V show the simulation and test results obtained for a battery pack system feeding a load, respectively. Afterward, Section VI discusses the results, and finally, Section VII concludes with the main contributions of the method.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The detection and location of ground faults in dc systems, such as PV power plants or batteries have been discussed in the literature. In this section, some of these studies are discussed.

A. Ground Fault Diagnosis in Solar Photovoltaic Systems

For PV systems, some ground faults diagnosis techniques are based on artificial neural network recognition from the voltage patterns generated by the switching transients of their power converters, or by fault current transients [6], [17], [18]. The data needed to train the neural networks will be bigger when more series-parallel cells are installed.

Other techniques use the output power and the positive and negative terminal current measurements of the PV strings to locate the ground fault [7]. It is important to highlight that this technique can be also used to detect other types of faults e.g., line to line ($L-L$) or short-circuited cells.

Since the RLC parameters of the cable change when a ground fault occurs, the frequency analysis of the current can also be used to detect ground faults [13].

The differential protection relays are another very common option for ground faults detection in dc systems. In [19], the ground fault location is calculated using multiple differential relays with communication. Furthermore, the detection of the PV faulty branch is commonly performed placing differential relays in each branch.

The discrimination of the faulty branch can also be done measuring the PV system grounding insulation resistance. If the insulation resistance is excessively low, there is a ground

fault in the system. Then, the variation of this parameter should be observed at the time the different branches are sequentially disconnected and connected. Only when the faulty branch is disconnected, the measurement suffers a considerable variation, returning to high values [20]. This method is also valid for battery storage systems [21].

Using the operation principles of travelling waves methods, some other works propose to inject specific current or voltage waves between ground and the neutral of the system [22]. This technique is known as spread spectrum time domain reflectometry. It allows the fault position location by measuring and analyzing the injected wave reflections in certain measure points. However, the error in the fault estimation increases considerably with the fault resistance as the fault current becomes smaller, and in most of cases, they cannot discern the faulty branch. Also, the injection methods are usually more expensive than the passive ones.

B. Ground Fault Diagnosis in Battery Storage Systems

Ground fault detection in battery storage systems is barely addressed in the literature, however, they can be the cause of fire or thermal-runaways in batteries [23]. Actual research is generally focused on methods to detect and locate internal short-circuits in batteries, which are commonly based on voltage, current and temperature cells measurements [24]. During a fault, abnormalities in these variables can be observed along the discharge cycle, and they can be used to detect possible cell short-circuits [25]. This type of diagnosis techniques need long sampling times to detect the fault because they are generally based on the registered battery charge/discharge cycle comparison with a healthy one.

For ground fault diagnosis, entropy-based methods [26] and artificial intelligence fault recognition [27] could be used. This diagnosis can be performed using the battery manage system, that requires numerous sensors which provides currents, voltages, and even temperature data in order to perform a complete fault diagnosis. With artificial intelligence, different type of faults can be discerned attending to the measured data patterns. These methods present good results in the detection process, but most of them require high sampling times or deep analysis after perceiving the fault to locate its position.

Other studies in this field detect the fault observing the difference between the current measurement and a certain calculated [28]. If this difference is greater than a certain threshold, a fault signal is emitted. In [29], the neutral voltage monitoring is recommended for ground fault detection when the batteries are connected in cascade.

In order to diagnose ground faults in the ac or dc sides of a variable speed drive some devices have been developed. Previous authors' investigations in this field were focused on the discrimination between ac and dc faults, using a grounding resistor in the midpoint of the dc bus for dc/ac systems [30] and in the neutral of an ac grid transformer for ac/ac drives [31]. By observing the frequency components of the voltage measure in this resistor the fault was detected and discerned between dc positive or negative pole faults, or ac side (grid or controlled sides) faults. However, these previous methods could

TABLE I
STATE OF THE ART METHODS' COMPARISON

Method	Ref.	Detects	Locates	Observations
Photovoltaic Systems				
Artificial Intelligence	[6],[17],[18]	✓	✓ [6],[17]	They need data and algorithm training
ANSI 87	[7],[19]	✓	✓ [19]	With communication between relays
Frequency response	[13]	✓		Early Fault detection
Insulation measurement	[20]	✓	✓ Only branch	It needs branch connection/disconnection
SSTDR	[22]	✓	✓	It needs voltage injection
Battery storage systems				
Insulation measurement	[20],[21]	✓	✓ [20] Only branch	It Needs branch connection/disconnection
Entropy methods	[26]	✓	✓	Long time required for a proper diagnosis
Artificial Intelligence	[27]	✓	✓	It Needs data and algorithm training
Model comparison	[28]	✓		
Neutral voltage monitoring	[29]	✓		Only for cascade ground isolated systems
Previous author's method	[30],[31]	✓		It discerns between AC or DC faulty side, but it does not locate the fault.
Proposed method		✓	✓	Valid for any type of DC source (only for ground faults)

only detect the faulty pole, but not the fault location. The problem resides in the impossibility of discriminating between the fault position and the fault resistance effects with only measuring the grounding resistor voltage in the dc midpoint/neutral of the system. Moreover, these previous methods are insensitive to dc midpoint or neutral faults.

Table I sums up the state of the art section and compares the methods with the proposed one. The method presented in this article introduces a ground fault location approach for dc systems that only needs the dc voltage component of a grounding resistor that switches between the midpoint, positive and negative terminals of the monitored dc system. To discern the faulty branch, the method requires the measurement of the output currents in all the branches.

Regarding the previous literature, the main contributions of the proposed method are as follows:

- 1) The installation of three switches in the dc side between a grounding resistor and three points of the electric circuit allow the online fault detection, and fault position and severity estimations inside a branch.
- 2) The output current measurement of each branch allows the branch discerning once the position and severity have been calculated.
- 3) The method can locate faults in the whole dc side of the system, which improves the authors' previous works [30], [31], that cannot detect faults in the dc midpoint because of system symmetry.
- 4) The method does not need artificial intelligence algorithms nether external signal injection.

However, with the implementation of three switches, the use of an additional microcontroller to manage them and electrical interlock is needed among them to avoid short circuits.

Fig. 1. Simplified scheme of the ground fault location method for dc systems with multiple grounding connections.

III. OPERATION PRINCIPLES OF THE DC GROUND FAULT LOCATION METHOD

As the ground faults are one of the most common types of faults in electric systems, a new method to locate this type of faults in dc systems is here presented. The method is focused on dc sources diagnosis. It provides information about the percentage of the dc source where the fault is k (i.e., the cell in fault in case of batteries or solar panels) and about the fault resistance R_f which is a direct indicator of the fault severity. In case of battery-packs in parallel, the method can also discern the faulty branch.

To solve the drawbacks presented in [30] and [31] this article proposes an updated method to locate dc ground faults. As the previous method, it incorporates a grounding resistor R_{gnd} . Additionally, the proposed system incorporates three switches as shown in Fig. 1. They allow the connection of R_{gnd} to the dc midpoint, the positive and the negative terminals in order to obtain different voltages in R_{gnd} . For the three different positions the positive terminal U_{gnd+} , dc midpoint U_{gndM} , and negative terminal, U_{gnd-} voltages are measured, respectively.

Once the grounding resistor has been connected, some possibilities can occur. In case of healthy state operation, there is not fault current that returns through R_{gnd} , consequently, the grounding resistor voltage U_{gnd} , will be zero in all the measurements. In case of fault, there exist three possibilities. First a ground fault occurs in the positive side (between the midpoint and the positive terminal). In this case, the voltage U_{gndM} measured in the midpoint connection, will have negative polarity. Second, a ground fault occurs in the negative side. Then, U_{gndM} will have positive polarity. The fault current distributions can be seen in Fig. 2 for each position and fault type. Finally, a ground fault in the midpoint, that implies null U_{gndM} .

The objective of measuring U_{gnd+} and U_{gnd-} is to obtain the absolute faulty voltage between terminals considering R_f . Therefore, U_{gnd} depends on the R_{gnd} switched position as follows:

$$U_{gndM} = - \left(k - \frac{1}{2} \right) U_{DC} \cdot \frac{R_{gnd}}{R_{gnd} + R_f} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Ground fault circuits with multiple switching positions. Two ground faults plotted [cases (a)–(c): switching in negative, midpoint and positive terminals for a positive pole ground fault; cases (d)–(f): switching in negative, midpoint and positive terminals for a negative pole ground fault].

$$U_{\text{gnd}+} = (1 - k) U_{\text{DC}} \cdot \frac{R_{\text{gnd}}}{R_{\text{gnd}} + R_f} \quad (2)$$

$$U_{\text{gnd}-} = -k U_{\text{DC}} \cdot \frac{R_{\text{gnd}}}{R_{\text{gnd}} + R_f} \quad (3)$$

Then, (1) corresponds to the midpoint, (2) to the positive and (3) to the negative connections. Then, the dual problem (k , R_f) of the previous method [30], [31] is solved, as the ground fault could be located using (4) from (1), (2), and (3)

$$k = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{U_{\text{gnd}M}}{U_{\text{gnd}+} - U_{\text{gnd}-}} \right) \quad (4)$$

where k is the fault position expressed in p.u (negative terminal $k = 0$ / positive terminal $k = 1$).

Once calculated k , the value of R_f can be estimated as

$$R_f = R_{\text{gnd}} \left[\frac{-(k - 1/2) \cdot U_{\text{DC}}}{U_{\text{gnd}M}} - 1 \right] \text{ for } k \neq 0.5 \quad (5)$$

$$R_f = R_{\text{gnd}} \left[\frac{-k \cdot U_{\text{DC}}}{U_{\text{gnd}-}} - 1 \right] \text{ for } k \neq 0 \quad (6)$$

$$R_f = -R_{\text{gnd}} \left[\frac{(1 - k) \cdot U_{\text{DC}}}{U_{\text{gnd}+}} - 1 \right] \text{ for } k \neq 1. \quad (7)$$

The results obtained for R_f by these three (5)–(7) are similar. However, different equations should be used attending to k . If the fault is near to the midpoint of the whole dc source, the (5) would have less accuracy, then it is recommendable to use (6) or

Fig. 3. Current distribution for a ground fault in the positive pole of a battery branch [In blue: fault current circulation; In red: current to the power system].

(7). This process should be taken analogously to the other two cases.

In case of dc systems with parallel branches (for example: electric vehicle batteries or PV arrays), the faulty branch can be identified by measuring the currents through all the parallel branches. The grounded branch would supply the ground fault current to the faulty branch (see Fig. 3). This means that the faulty branch would supplies less current to the power system and the grounded branch would supplies more. In Fig. 3, it can be seen that the healthy ungrounded branches would supply a dc current, I_{DCH} . The faulty branch would support a dc current ($I_{\text{DCH}} - I_{\text{DCF}}$) lower than the other branches to the power system, as the ground fault current would return to ground due to the

Fig. 4. Simulation equivalent circuit of a battery cell.

TABLE II
DC SOURCE PARAMETERS

Parameter	Nomenclature	Magnitude
Battery chemistry	Ni-Cd	
Total DC bus voltage	U_{DC}	484 V
Cell equivalent circuit parameters	U_{Cell}	1.3 V
	R_0	5 m Ω
	R_1	10 m Ω
	C_1	10 ⁴ F
	R_2	0.305 Ω
	C_2	1.5 \times 10 ⁴ F
Cells per branch	Cell/Branch	372
Parallel Branches	Branches	6

internal fault. The grounded branch would supply more current ($I_{DCH} + I_{DCF}$) to the power system because the ground fault current returns through R_{gnd} to the branch midpoint.

To sum up, by measuring the grounding resistor voltages at the three points and also by measuring the output current from each branch, the fault can be located in k , R_f and branch.

IV. COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

To validate the proposed method, numerous simulations have been carried out in MATLAB-Simulink. The simulation model is displayed in Figs. 4 and 5

A. Simulation Model Description

The simulation model consists of a dc/ac power system fed by Nickel-Cadmium batteries. The rated dc voltage is 484 V comprising 372 cells. Each cell is modelled with its equivalent circuit as shown in Fig. 4 and its main parameters are given in Table II.

In Fig. 5, it can be also seen that some points between positive and negative poles are accessible to perform ground faults after defining the percentage of cells where the fault is located, k . Furthermore, six branches have been modeled and their output currents I_{DC} are measured in the positive terminal.

Then, a grounding resistor of 4.7 k Ω (to limit the fault current to 50 mA) with switches in the positive, midpoint and negative terminals has been placed in the first branch. Afterward, its voltage is measured U_{gnd} .

The output terminals of the battery pack are connected to a Six-Pulses Inverter that feeds a three-phase RL load of $50 + j\omega 2 \times 10^{-5} \Omega$ per phase. The inverter's commutation elements used are IGBTs, but other technologies such as SiC transistors could be implemented because the commutation elements have not influence in the fault circuit, which is closed only in the dc side. To add more relevance to the ac side, some inductive filters, mutual capacitances, and parasitic capacitances-to-ground are

TABLE III
SIMULATION SETUP PARAMETERS

Component	Characteristic	Magnitude
Grounding resistor	R_{gnd}	4700 Ω
Cable resistance	R_w	1 Ω
Cable inductance	L_w	16 μ H
Converter	C	1.638 mF
	R_{int}	1 m Ω
	$R_{Smubber}$	1000 Ω
	$C_{Smubber}$	1 nF
AC inductive filter	L_{filter}	0.3 mH
Inductive load	R	50 Ω
	L	20 μ H

included in the model. Table III sums up the rest of parameters of the simulation model.

B. Healthy State Simulation

First of all, a healthy-state simulation case should be performed. As no ground fault exists, the voltage in the grounding resistor U_{gnd} should be zero or near zero. High frequency noises can appear in U_{gnd} due to the parasitic capacitances to ground in the ac side of the inverter, which are shown in Fig. 5.

The results of this simulation are plotted in Figs. 6 and 7, where U_{gnd} and the branches' currents are shown, respectively. As expected, the U_{gnd} is null due to the absence of fault currents (see Fig. 6). Furthermore, the equilibrium of current in all the branches is achieved, reaching a dc value of 0.8567 A for each of the six branches (see Fig. 7). Both figures display a simulation time of 150 ms where the positive and negative breakers are activated at 60 and 120 ms, respectively. For the three connections, the voltage achieved in Fig. 6 still being the same.

C. Ground Fault Simulations

Afterward, some faults have been performed varying their cell location k the fault resistance R_f and the faulty branch. Each of these parameters can be detected according to (4), to (5)–(7) and by observing which branch has less output current, respectively. The faults have been performed at $k = 0, 10, 20, \dots, 100\%$ of the battery pack with R_f of 0 Ω , 2.3 k Ω , 4.7 k Ω , and 10 k Ω for each of the six branches.

Fig. 8(a) and (b) shows the grounding resistor voltages U_{gnd} for a 150 ms simulation test varying k with constant R_f to analyze the fault position effect. The faults collected in Fig. 8(a) are performed for $R_f = 0 \Omega$, $k = [50\%, 100\%]$ in the first branch (left batteries branch in Fig. 5). On the other hand, Fig. 8(b) shows faults carried out in $k = [0\%, 40\%]$ for the same R_f and branch. The simulations start with the grounding resistor connected to the dc midpoint. In the same way as the healthy state simulation, the switching to positive and negative poles are at 60 and 120 ms, respectively. The results show that the effects of k in U_{gnd} are mainly two. The first is related to the U_{gndM} polarity, which is a fast indicator of the fault position: if the fault takes place in the negative side ($k < 50\%$), U_{gnd} will have positive polarity and vice versa for positive side faults. The second is related to the amplitude achieved in U_{gnd+} and U_{gnd-} : for positive side ground faults, the negative terminal position reaches higher U_{gnd}

Fig. 5. Simulation model [from left to right: grounding resistor and switchers to positive, midpoint and negative terminals; battery branches with 372 cells each branch divided in four with fault points accessible and their branch-current measurement device; wire resistance and inductance; inverter capacitor; inverter IGBTs and PWM control; filter inductances; parasitic capacitances and RL load].

Fig. 6. Grounding resistor voltage during a healthy-state simulation.

Fig. 7. Branch currents during a healthy-state simulation.

values and vice versa. In any case, the difference $U_{gnd+} - U_{gnd-}$ remains constant for any k and constant R_f .

Analogously, Fig. 8(c) and (d) show U_{gnd} changes for different R_f and constant k to analyze the fault resistance effect. Some simulations have been carried out with two locations $k = 70\%$ [see Fig. 8(c)] and 30% [see Fig. 8(d)] and R_f of 0Ω , $2.3 \text{ k}\Omega$, $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$, and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$. These simulations show that the higher fault resistance the lower the grounding resistor voltage. However, the

U_{gnd} measurements for all the switching positions are attenuated in the same proportion, thus, as stated in (4) the fault location is not affected by R_f . Furthermore, it can be appreciated that higher values of R_f implies more circulation of parasitic currents from the capacitances to ground of the ac side, although, they should not affect the location method as it is based on the dc components.

In order to locate the faulty branch, the output current measurement should be performed. In this case, a fault location ($k = 70\%$) and a fault resistance ($R_f = 0 \Omega$) have been simulated for different faulty branches. Two examples of ground faults, one in the branch 1 and other in the branch 4, are plotted in Figs. 9 and 10, respectively. In case of a ground fault in branch 1, the current in branch 1 has a dc value of 853.1 mA and the other five currents are identical between them, and they have a value of 857.3 mA . In a ground fault in branch 4, the currents repeat the same pattern. As the faulty branch is the fourth, the output current in this branch reaches the lower value among the six simulated ($I_{DC4} = 842.9 \text{ mA}$, where the other currents are 857.3 mA). Additionally, the branch 1 reaches the highest current value due to the fault current recirculation through R_{gnd} ($I_{DC1} = 867.5 \text{ mA}$).

Finally, Table IV sums up the branch currents and grounding resistor voltages for some different ground fault locations. It can be seen that for faults located far away from the dc midpoint, the fault current is higher than for faults near this point. A problem appears when the fault is in the dc midpoint, in this case, the current should be analyzed in other switching position, e.g., switching to the positive terminal, where the faulty branch will be the one that presents the maximum output current as it can be observed in Figs. 9 and 10, respectively.

With this analysis in a grounding resistor, the fault location k its severity (in terms of fault resistance R_f) and the faulty branch (by measuring the output currents in the branches) can be

Fig. 8. U_{gnd} measurements for different simulations with fault [(a) U_{gnd} for ground faults, $k = 50\%$ – 100% and $R_f = 0 \Omega$. (b) U_{gnd} for ground faults, $k = 0\%$ – 40% and $R_f = 0 \Omega$. (c) U_{gnd} for ground faults, $k = 70\%$ and $R_f = 0 \Omega, 2.3, 4.7,$ and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$. (d) U_{gnd} for ground faults, $k = 30\%$ and $R_f = 0 \Omega, 2.3 \text{ k}\Omega, 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$ and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$].

TABLE IV
SIMULATION RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT GROUND FAULT LOCATIONS

Simulation	Fault location parameters			Voltage measurements [V]			Branch current measurements [mA]					
	Branch	R_f	k	U_{gndM}	$U_{\text{gnd+}}$	$U_{\text{gnd-}}$	I_{DC1}	I_{DC2}	I_{DC3}	I_{DC4}	I_{DC5}	I_{DC6}
1	1	0	0	240	481	0	834.9	860.3	860.3	860.3	860.3	860.3
2	1	0	10	192	433	-48	842.7	859.1	859.1	859.1	859.1	859.1
3	1	0	20	144	385	-96	848.9	858.1	858.1	858.1	858.1	858.1
4	1	0	30	97	337	-143	853.3	857.5	857.5	857.5	857.5	857.5
5	1	0	40	49	290	-191	856	857	857	857	857	857
6	1	0	50	0	240	-240	856.9	856.9	856.9	856.9	856.9	856.9
7	1	0	60	-49	191	-290	856	857	857	857	857	857
8	1	0	70	-97	143	-337	853.3	857.5	857.6	857.7	857.8	857.9
9	1	0	80	-144	96	-385	848.9	858.1	858.1	858.1	858.1	858.1
10	1	0	90	-192	48	-433	842.7	859.1	859.1	859.1	859.1	859.1
11	1	0	100	-240	0	-481	834.8	860.3	860.3	860.3	860.3	860.3
12	1	2.3	70	-65	96	-226	854.5	857.3	857.3	857.3	857.3	857.3
13	1	4.7	70	-48	71	-169	855.1	857.2	857.2	857.2	857.2	857.2
14	1	10	70	-31	45	-108	855.7	857.1	857.1	857.1	857.1	857.1
15	2	10	70	-30	46	-108	860.4	852.5	857.1	857.1	857.1	857.1
16	3	10	70	-30	46	-108	860.4	857.1	852.5	857.1	857.1	857.1
17	4	10	70	-30	46	-108	860.4	857.1	857.1	852.5	857.1	857.1
18	5	10	70	-30	46	-108	860.4	857.1	857.1	857.1	852.5	857.1
19	6	10	70	-30	46	-108	860.4	857.1	857.1	857.1	857.1	852.5

The bold values indicate the faulty branch.

Fig. 9. Branches' current for a fault in branch 1, $k = 70\%$ and $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

Fig. 10. Branches' current for a fault in branch 4, $k = 70\%$ and $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

Fig. 11. Experimental setup [(1) four-branches battery; (2) R load; (3) circuit breaker; (4) wire interconnections; (5) R_{gnd} ; (6) controlled switches, (7): microcontroller; (8) voltage sensor; (9) current sensor; (10) oscilloscope; (11) R_f ; and (12) faulty point].

estimated without long time analysis or without using complex artificial intelligence methods.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to validate the fundamentals of the method and the simulation results, several experimental tests have been carried out.

A. Experimental Setup Description

The experimental setup, which is displayed in Fig. 11, consists of a battery (1) with four parallel branches. Each branch has 24 cells of $1.5 V_{\text{DC}}/\text{cell}$. Therefore, the total voltage is $36 V_{\text{DC}}$.

To emulate the electric energy consumption, a resistive load (2), $R = 100 \Omega$, has been connected to the battery pack by a circuit breaker (3). The battery cells were connected in series, enabling interconnections (4) every four cells, and keeping the four branches' midpoints accessible.

A grounding resistor $R_{\text{gnd}} = 1.1 \text{ k}\Omega$ (5) has been installed in the first branch. Three controlled switches (6) vary the R_{gnd} connection among the dc midpoint, positive and negative terminals positions. These switches are controlled with a microcontroller (7). The switches are closed along a time of $t = 50 \text{ ms}$ each, and in order to avoid cells' short-circuits, a dead time among commutations of $t_d = 10 \text{ ms}$ was set.

Once the electric circuit is installed, a voltage sensor (8) is connected in terminals of R_{gnd} and three current sensors (9) are installed in the branches 1, 2, and 4, respectively. These sensors send the information of U_{gnd} , $I_{\text{DC}1}$, $I_{\text{DC}2}$, and $I_{\text{DC}4}$ to a four-channels oscilloscope (10). Finally, ground faults are performed connecting a fault resistor (11) with $R_f = 0, 600$, and 1200Ω between a faulty point (12), that can vary between the branches and each 4 battery cells, and ground. The values of R_f correspond approximately with 0%, 50%, and 100% of R_{gnd} .

B. Healthy State Experimental Tests

To corroborate that the experimental setup works properly in healthy conditions, a measurement was carried out obtaining the results plotted in Figs. 12 and 13. In Fig. 12, U_{gnd} is displayed for the three commutation points obtaining in all of them the same measurement. As there is no fault current, $U_{\text{gnd}M}$, $U_{\text{gnd}+}$,

Fig. 12. Experimental test under healthy conditions: U_{gnd} measurement.

Fig. 13. Experimental test under healthy conditions: branch currents measurement.

and $U_{\text{gnd}-}$ are null. In Fig. 13, I_1 , I_2 , and I_4 can be seen. The currents have the same value, as the system is balanced.

C. Ground Fault Experimental Tests

After checking the correct operation of the method under healthy state conditions, different ground faults were performed. As each branch has packs of 4 cells, the points $k = 0, 16.7, 33.3, 50, 66.7, 83.3$, and 100% of each branch were accessible.

In Fig. 14(a) and (b) different ground faults were performed for zero fault resistance, $R_f = 0 \Omega$, but for different fault positions inside the same branch (first branch). The results show how $U_{\text{gnd}M}$ varies from negative values to positive values when the faults are in the positive or negative side of the battery respectively. Also, $U_{\text{gnd}+}$ and $U_{\text{gnd}-}$ notice higher voltages when farther away they are from the faulty point (i.e., $U_{\text{gnd}+}$ higher

Fig. 14. Grounding resistor voltage U_{gnd} for different faults [(a) U_{gnd} for positive side ground faults, $k \geq 50\%$ and $R_f = 0 \Omega$. (b) U_{gnd} for negative side ground faults, $k < 50\%$ and $R_f = 0 \Omega$. (c) U_{gnd} for positive side ground faults, $k = 66.7\%$ and $R_f = 0, 600, \text{ and } 1200 \Omega$. (d) U_{gnd} for negative side ground faults, $k = 33.3\%$ and $R_f = 0, 600, \text{ and } 1200 \Omega$].

TABLE V
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT GROUND FAULT LOCATIONS

Test	Fault parameters			Measured voltage			Measured currents			Fault parameters estimation				
	N ^o	Branch	R_f (Ω)	x (%)	U_{gndM} [V]	$U_{\text{gnd}+}$ [V]	$U_{\text{gnd}-}$ [V]	I_{DC1} [mA]	$I_{DC2} \approx I_{DC3}$ [mA]	I_d [mA]	x (%)	R_{fM} (Ω)	R_{f-} (Ω)	R_{f+} (Ω)
1	1	0	0.0	18.2	36.7	0.02	84.02	89.91	87.37	0.42%	67.4	63.1	-9836	1
2	1	0	16.7	12.2	30.5	-6.00	85.97	88.11	87.35	16.6%	74.7	72.4	86.4	1
3	1	0	33.3	6.10	24.5	-12.1	87.72	88.95	86.71	33.3%	73.1	68.0	83.5	4 (fail)
4	1	0	50.0	0.04	18.4	-18.2	94.45	89.68	88.05	49.9%	72.8	69.4	76.2	4 (fail)
5	1	0	66.7	-6.02	12.3	-24.4	87.97	89.40	86.63	66.4%	67.2	69.6	66.0	4 (fail)
6	1	0	83.3	-12.1	6.21	-30.6	86.57	89.91	86.98	82.9%	65.5	78.7	62.9	1
7	1	0	100.0	-18.2	0.05	-36.7	94.72	90.60	87.94	99.4%	67.4	3814	62.2	4 (fail)
8	1	600	16.7	8.67	21.7	-4.30	85.97	88.11	87.35	16.7%	549.5	546.6	564.3	1
9	1	600	66.7	-4.30	8.76	-17.3	87.97	89.40	86.63	66.6%	546.7	541.3	549.4	4 (fail)
10	1	1200	16.7	6.64	16.8	-3.39	85.97	88.11	87.35	17.2%	1010	1074	1022	1
11	1	1200	66.7	-3.37	6.71	-13.5	87.97	89.40	86.63	66.7%	1024	1030	1020	4 (fail)
12	2	600	66.7	-4.28	8.50	-17.1	87.00	83.06	84.81	66.7%	574.5	580.3	571.6	2
13	4	600	16.7	8.67	21.7	-4.32	85.04	89.04	87.52	16.7%	547.4	545.5	556.8	1 (fail)
14	2	1200	66.7	-3.33	6.62	-13.3	87.00	83.06	84.81	66.7%	1050	1057	1047	2
15	4	1200	16.7	6.60	16.7	-3.38	85.04	89.04	87.52	17.2%	1033	1023	1085	1 (fail)

The bold values indicate the faulty branch.

values will appear for negative side faults and $U_{\text{gnd}-}$ higher values will appear for positive side faults) as there are more cells involved in the fault circuit. However, as in simulations, it can be appreciated that the difference $U_{\text{gnd}+} - U_{\text{gnd}-}$ remains constant for a same R_f .

In Fig. 14(c) and (d), the position of the fault is constant in two different positions ($k = 66.7\%$ and 33.3% , respectively) to study the effect of R_f . In this way, fault resistances of $R_f = 0, 600, \text{ and } 1200 \Omega$ were used. The effect shown in this case is the attenuation of the voltage signal in all the switch positions, as there are lower currents flowing through R_{gnd} . An important difference compared with Fig. 14(a) and (b) resides in that

$U_{\text{gnd}+} - U_{\text{gnd}-}$ does not remain constant with changes in R_f . As in simulation results, this attenuation is the same for U_{gndM} , $U_{\text{gnd}+}$, and $U_{\text{gnd}-}$, then, R_f has not influence in the position calculation as shown in (4).

The numerical results of the different fault locations are collected in Table V. The fault location k presents good results as well as fault resistance estimation. However, the branch estimation shows certain deficiencies due to the small variations in the currents.

Despite the method presents good branch estimation in the simulations, the experimental test does not provide the same results for the currents observation during the midpoint terminal

Fig. 15. Branch currents for a ground fault in $k = 83.3\%$, $R_f = 600 \Omega$ of the branch 1.

Fig. 16. Branch currents for a ground fault in $k = 83.3\%$, $R_f = 600 \Omega$ of the branch 4.

Fig. 17. Theoretical comparison versus experimental and simulation results for constant R_f and k variations.

operation. However, as it can be observed in Figs. 15 and 16, it could be a good option that, after estimating k and R_f , the farthest switch would be used to locate the branch, e.g., if the fault is in the positive side, the lower current presented during the negative switch conduction time should be the branch in fault and analogously for negative faults.

VI. RESULTS DISCUSSION

The results show two different tendencies attending to the estimated fault parameters (k , R_f , and faulty branch).

A. Fault Location Inside a Branch, k and R_f , Estimation

In terms of fault location k along inside the series cells of a single branch, the method provides excellent results. In Fig. 17, the theoretical approach can be compared with the simulations (+) and the experimental tests (•) for different fault locations with the same fault resistance. The curves' slopes are

Fig. 18. Theoretical comparison versus experimental and simulation results for constant k and R_f variations [blue: $k = 16.7\%$ experiments; red: $k = 70\%$ simulation].

Fig. 19. Theoretical comparison versus experimental and simulation results for k and R_f variations.

directly linked to the fault resistance, as well as the difference $U_{\text{gnd}+}(k) - U_{\text{gnd}-}(k)$. The voltage values are normalized attending to the maximum dc voltage U_{DC} . The normalization is also applied to R_f attending to the R_{gnd} value. This normalization allow the comparison between simulations and experimental tests.

The fault resistance effect is summed up in Fig. 18 for two different positions. In this figure, a parallel displacement can be seen attending to k variations for $U_{\text{gnd}M}$, $U_{\text{gnd}+}$, and $U_{\text{gnd}-}$. It can be also noticed an attenuation of their relative distances with the increase of R_f . In this case, simulations are plotted in red and compared with a theoretical fault in $k = 70\%$, and experimental tests are plotted in blue and compared with a theoretical fault in $k = 16.7\%$.

Finally, both effects (k , R_f) can be observed in Fig. 19 from the theoretical approach, the simulations, and the experimental results. It can be seen that for low R_f and $k = 0\%$, $U_{\text{gnd}+}$ reach its maximum, whereas for low R_f and $k = 100\%$ it is $U_{\text{gnd}-}$ which reach its minimum. Also, U_{gnd} will be zero for whatever R_f is meanwhile the switch position match with the fault position, e.g., $U_{\text{gnd}M} = 0$ for $k = 50\%$.

In terms of accuracy, k estimations reach errors up to $\pm 0.60\%$ in experiments and R_f reach estimations errors up to $\pm 190 \Omega$ for high fault resistances ($R_f = 1.2 \text{ k}\Omega$).

B. Faulty Branch Estimation

The faulty branch estimation has presented good results in the simulations but not in the experimental tests.

This failure in the experimental tests can be provoked by unbalance between branch voltages. In this way, the branches with lower charge will produce lower output currents, and then, they could be detected erroneously as branch in fault. For this reason, this hypothesis cannot be considered uniquely for the dc midpoint position. It could be a good option to consider the branches currents when the farthest switch to the fault is connected (once k was estimated). Then, higher current variations will be achieved in order to avoid the lack of selectivity that the dc midpoint presents. For example, for a fault in $k = 83.3\%$, $R_f = 600 \Omega$ in branch 4 (see Fig. 16), the lower current is clearly observed during the negative switch conduction for the branch 4.

Despite of the lack of selectivity in the branch discerning, the method presents good results in the cell location and considering the switch position to examine the branch in fault this problem could be easily solved.

If the proposed method is compared with previous works in terms of accuracy in the series cell location, k (which is the main problem in the fault location for dc sources), the proposed method obtains maximum absolute errors of 0.6% and it has a good sensitivity even for $R_f = 1.2 \text{ k}\Omega$, where in [6] the maximum error reaches 5.76% with $R_f = 0 \Omega$; in [17] the probability of estimation failure of the faulty cell is 1.69% for a maximum $R_f = 25 \Omega$; or in [19] the maximum error seen is 6.24% for $R_f = 2 \Omega$.

Then, this method provides a good alternative for dc ground fault location in dc sources with multiple series-parallel cells.

VII. CONCLUSION

The dc sources, such as PV panels and batteries are highly increasing with the development of smart grids, renewable energy, and electric vehicles. One of the main problems is the protection and location of ground faults due to their complex topologies.

In this article, a method to detect and locate ground faults for dc sources is proposed. It is based on a voltage analysis in a grounding resistor connected cyclically between the midpoint, the positive and the negative terminals of the dc source and ground. The grounding resistor is connected by three switches. The relative difference between the positive and negative terminal voltages and the voltage measured in the midpoint position allows the fault location and fault resistance calculation inside a branch. Moreover, in case of multiple parallel branches dc power sources, if the output current in each branch is measured, the faulty branch can be located as the branch that presents the lower current in the farthest switch connection to the fault.

To corroborate the method numerous simulations were performed in MATLAB-Simulink achieving positive results in series and parallel location. Furthermore, numerous experimental tests were carried out obtaining excellent results for fault location and fault resistance estimation inside a branch, but not at all for the parallel branch estimation.

Nevertheless, some future research should be done in finding alternative methods for branch discrimination and for testing the proposed method in real facilities.

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